

The Efficacy of Hyperbaric Oxygen Therapy versus Low Level Laser Therapy on Transcutaneous Oxygen Saturation for Venous Leg Ulcer

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Abstract

Background and Purpose

Venous ulcers are most common kind of chronic leg ulcers represents about 60 to 80% and considered the main cause of morbidity. Hyperbaric Oxygen therapy recorded significant improvement of wound healing and tissue repair at all stages.

Wound healing was one of the first areas in which the effect of Low Level Laser Therapy was investigated; laser irradiation is releasing of Vascular Endothelial Growth Factor (VEGF) which stimulates not only angiogenesis but also endothelial cell growth.

This study investigated the effect of Hyperbaric oxygen therapy versus Low level laser therapy on transcutaneous oxygen saturation (TcPo₂) at the margin of chronic leg ulcers

Patients and Methods

Forty patients with chronic venous ulcers suffering for more than 6 weeks without improvement, their ages ranged from 20 - 60 were included in the present study. Those patients were classified randomly into 2 groups of equal number, 20 patients for each group. The first group (Group A) was treated with Low Level Laser Therapy by Scanner Infrared diode laser with wavelengths 880 and 950 nanometer- Energy density 5 Joul/ cm² - time of session depended on ulcer parameters (once daily for repeated 10 days) and the second group (Group B) was treated with Hyperbaric Oxygen Therapy by Hyperbaric oxygen chamber at pressure 1.5 Bar, time of session 90 minutes with 60 minutes breathing 100 % pure oxygen through the individual mask (once daily for repeated 10 sessions).

Results

Hyperbaric oxygen therapy get the higher mean value recorded 1.884 ± 0.506 . While the mean value of low level laser therapy recorded 0.265 ± 0.529 .

Conclusion

Improving the microcirculation and increasing transcutaneous oxygen saturation to the ulcer region with hyperbaric oxygen therapy was more than low level diode laser.

Keywords

Transcutaneous; Oxygen Saturation; Hyperbaric; Oxygen Therapy; Low Level Laser; Diode Laser

Introduction

There are many types of chronic leg ulcers, most patients with venous leg ulcers from around 60 to 80 percent [1].

This is one of the main causes of morbidity affecting the social and economic conditions of any country [2]. Transcutaneous oxygen saturation (TcPo₂) at ulcer margins is one of the widespread methods of measuring partial oxygen pressure dissolved in liquid after penetration of skin levels [3].

In literature, TcPo₂ reflects the underlying micro vascular circulation, used to determine peripheral vascular diseases, wound healing assessments, hyperbaric oxygen therapy indications and improvements [4].

Statement of the problem

The delayed ulceration healing and its effects on rate of recovery and period of hospitalization are serious and functional problem, therefore, the selection of the appropriate treatment modalities is one of big challenges to deal with these patients.

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Design of the study

This study conducted at Kobri El Kobe Medical Complex, Hyperbaric Oxygen therapy and Foot Care Rehabilitation Center in the period from March 2019 to June 2019.

Patients accepted the experimental study and signed an acceptance approval paper before the beginning of the study

Purpose of the study

This study was designed to evaluate the effect of HBO versus LLLT on transcutaneous oxygen saturation for chronic venous leg ulcers which assessed by one method of evaluative approaches.

Subjects

Forty patients with long lasting chronic venous ulcers suffering from more than 6 weeks without improvement classified randomly into two groups:

Group A: 20 patients treated with low level diode laser therapy.
Group B: 20 patients treated with hyperbaric oxygen therapy.

Inclusive Criteria

- Patient's ages ranged from 20-65.
- All patients are diabetic controlled.
- Patient's cardiac ejection fraction must be ≥ 45 was evaluated pre sessions for one time, and blood pressure must be $\leq 150/90$ mm\Hg measured pre each session.
- All patients are free from chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, lung fibrosis, pleural effusion and pneumonia .
- All patients' ears are clinically evaluated to tolerate pressure therapy

Equipments

The equipment in the present study was delimited into two main equipments

Therapeutic equipment

1. Hyperbaric oxygen chamber at pressure 1.5 Bar, total time of session is 90 minutes included 60 minutes breathing 100% pure oxygen through the individual mask.
2. Scanner Infrared diode laser (wavelengths 880 and 950 nm-Energy density 5J/ cm² - time of session depended on ulcer parameters) used to focus perpendicular upon the site of venous ulcer with a distance not less than 60 cm.

The sessions repeated once daily for 10 days.

Measurement equipment

Transcutaneous hemoglobin saturation with oxygen: Superficial electrode with an individual membrane inserted adhesive to the ulcer margin. The steps for TcPo₂ measuring were recorded at the main chamber monitor (Model Module Box 84 TE-serial number: 0216 - 1021-0211).

The measurements were done pre treatment and after 10 days through the study. Time for each evaluation was pre the treatment procedures.

Results

Transcutaneous oxygen saturation for both groups

The mean value of the differences of ulcer TcPo₂ between the pre treatment ulcer Tc Po₂ and after 10 days of treatment by low level laser in relation to the pre treatment TcPo₂ of Group A was 0.265 ± 0.529 .

The mean value of the difference of ulcer TcPo₂ between the pre treatment ulcer Tc Po₂ and after 10 days of treatment by hyperbaric oxygen in relation to the pre treatment TcPo₂ of Group B was 1.884 ± 0.506 (Figure 1).

The difference between the mean values of increasing

Figure 1: Difference between the mean values and standard deviations of ulcer TcPo₂ between the pre treatment ulcer TcPo₂ and after ten sessions of treatment in relation to the pre treatment ulcer TcPo₂ of both groups

Statistical Group	Group A	Group B
Patients number	20 patients	20 patients
Ulcers number	26 ulcers	27 ulcers
Mean	0.256	1.884
S. D.±	0.529	0.506
Standard error	0.104	0.097

Table 1: Shows the difference between the mean values and standard deviations of ulcer TcPo₂ between the pre treatment ulcer TcPo₂ and after ten days of treatment in relation to the pre treatment ulcer TcPo₂ of both groups.

transcutaneous oxygen saturation between both groups are more in Group B than Group A (Table 1).

Discussion

Positive synergistic effects on tissue hyper oxygenation gained from combining hyperbaric oxygen therapy at 1.4 bar partial pressure and infrared therapy [5].

Hyperbaric oxygen therapy leads to increase partial pressure of arterial oxygen estimated by Henry's law [6] that explained the important role of HBO in tissue repair of the ischemic ulcers through improving energy metabolism and swelling reduction [7].

Building of new capillary network at the site of chronic ulcers requires adequate amount of oxygen concentration for the tissues to create a powerful angiogenesis' stimulus combined with fibroblastic proliferation leading to revascularization [8].

Low level laser therapy had serious effects on wound healing on a morphometric study for rats depending on cytokine level indicated that LLLT enhanced the initial level of the inflammatory stage as an important healing factor in chronic ulcer healing also depending on count of collagen fiber indicated that LLLT extended its effect to the remodeling stage of wound healing [9].

Another experimental study investigated the effects of low level laser therapy with wavelength 660nm, 2Joules/ulcer site on 45 old rats, and recorded high significant positive effects of LLLT on enhancement inflammatory agents and improvement of collagen production through the stages of ulcer healing [10].

Both HBOT and LLLT had positive effects on improving healing and tissue repair established by many studies either for animals or humans. Because tissue oxygenation concerned an important factor for all stages of wound healing and angiogenesis for ischemic tissues, this study concerned to record the level of transcutaneous oxygen saturation pre and post 10 sessions of treatments with both HBOT and LLLT.

Hyperbaric oxygen therapy get the higher mean value recorded 1.884 while the mean value of low level laser therapy recorded 0.256.

This result reflected the main effect of HBOT on tissue repair depending on increasing oxygen saturation but the main effect of LLLT needs more investigation. Further studies are recommended to investigate the effects of LLLT on oxygen saturation and the effects of combined therapy between HBOT and LLLT on rapid healing action for chronic ischemic ulcers.

Conclusion

Improving the microcirculation and increasing transcutaneous oxygen saturation to the ulcer region with hyperbaric Oxygen therapy was more than low level laser therapy.

References

1. Vasudevan B. Pathophysiology and classification of leg ulcers. *Indian Dermatology Online Journal*. 2014 Sep;5(3):366-370.
2. Millan BS. Venous Ulcers Diagnosis and Treatment. *Am Fam Physician*. 2019 Sep;100(5):298-305.
3. Kulcke A. Principels and contexts of tissue oxygenation imaging (HSI technology) and transcutaneous oxygen measurment in tissue (TcPo₂);2019.
4. Vincent E. Reference value of transcutaneous oxygen measurement in diabetic patients compared with nondiabetic patients. *J Vasc Surg*. 2008 Aug;48(2):382-388.
5. Dunnwald T. Combined Hyperbaric Oxygen Partial Pressure at 1.4 Bar with Infrared Radiation: A Useful Tool To Improve Tissue Hypoxemia. *Med Sci Monit*. 2018 Jun;24:4009-4019.
6. Latham E. Hyperbaric oxygen therapy. *Medscape*. 2009.
7. Niinikoski JH. Clinical hyperbaric oxygen therapy, wound perfusion and transcutaneous oximetry. *World Surgery Journal*. 2004 Mar;28(3):307-311.
8. Bhutani S, Vishwanath G. Hyperbaric oxygen and wound healing. *Indian Plast Surg Journal*. 2012 May;45(2):316-324.
9. Ramos FS. The effects of transcutaneous low-level laser therapy on the skin healing process: an experimental model. *Lasers Med Sci Journal*. 2018 Jul;33(5):967-976.
10. Fiorio FB. Photobiomodulation therapy action in wound repair skin induced in aged rats old: time course of biomarkers inflammatory and repair. *Lasers Med Sci Journal*. 2017 Nov;32(8):1769-1782.